

Linguistic Convergence and Identity Negotiation in Chinese-Bugis Communication in Soppeng Regency

By: Erni Majadiah

Silsan Group

Email: eimjdyh@gmail.com

Submission date: August 2025

Accepted date: October 2025

Published in: October 2025

Abstract:

This study analyses the dynamics of communication between the Chinese and Bugis ethnic groups in Soppeng Regency using a descriptive qualitative approach with participant observation and in-depth interviews with key informants from both ethnic groups. The focus of the study is the process of communicative adaptation and the mechanisms of social integration that are built in daily interactions. The findings show multidimensional communicative adaptation, including: (1) Linguistic convergence through the adoption of the Bugis language with the internalization of the concept of mappakatau and the use of the discursive particles "je" and "ki" as markers of solidarity; (2) Hybridity of nonverbal communication in gestures, color symbolism, and the concept of time; (3) Active religious tolerance through cross-participation in celebrations and voluntary conversion in interethnic marriages; (4) Involvement in the preservation of traditional Bugis arts; (5) Economic interdependence that strengthens community cohesion. The identified communication patterns show an "adaptive integration" strategy characterised by selective adoption, reciprocal accommodation, and maintenance of core identity while developing cross-cultural communicative competence. Interethnic communication in Soppeng is harmonious due to inclusive community leadership, economic interdependence, and a shared commitment to tolerance. This study provides lessons for the development of multicultural communication in the Indonesian context.

Keywords: Intercultural Communication, Linguistic Convergence, Ethnic Identity, Chinese-Bugis, Social Integration.

INTRODUCTION

Indonesia, as a country with more than 1,300 ethnic groups, faces complex challenges in managing harmonious intercultural communication. Ethnic diversity is a national treasure, but it also has the potential to trigger conflict if not managed properly. Various studies show that interethnic communication in Indonesia still faces significant obstacles, ranging from stereotypes and prejudice to open conflict that can disrupt social stability (Muchtar et al., 2019; Mulyana & Rakhmat, 2016). This

phenomenon is becoming increasingly relevant in the context of globalisation, which increases mobility and the intensity of interethnic contact.

Amidst this complexity, Soppeng Regency, South Sulawesi, shows an interesting phenomenon in interethnic communication, particularly between the Chinese and Bugis ethnic groups, which has been going on for several generations. Unlike other regions that often experience interethnic tensions, Soppeng shows a relatively harmonious and sustainable model of integration, where both ethnic groups have succeeded in establishing effective communication in various aspects of social, economic, and cultural life. This phenomenon is significant given the long history of Chinese ethnic relations with indigenous Indonesian communities, which have not always been smooth, especially during the New Order period, which implemented a policy of forced assimilation.

The Chinese ethnic group, as a minority group with an estimated population of around 1.2% to 2.8% of Indonesia's total population, has experienced various socio-political dynamics throughout history that have influenced their communication patterns with other ethnic groups. (Suryadinata, 2004). Meanwhile, the Bugis ethnic group, as one of the largest ethnic groups in South Sulawesi with a population of around 4 million in the region (the national estimate reaches 6-7 million), has a strong cultural tradition, a relatively inclusive social system, and a long history as traders and sailors who are accustomed to interacting with various ethnic groups (Mattulada, 1995). The combination of the characteristics of these two ethnic groups creates conditions conducive to the development of a unique model of interethnic communication.

Studies of interethnic communication in Indonesia have developed significantly in the last two decades, but there is still a considerable gap in understanding the communication mechanisms that enable interethnic harmony. Research (Mughtar et al., 2019) On intercultural communication provides a comprehensive theoretical framework for understanding the dynamics of communication in a pluralistic society, while Mulyana (2016) explores various barriers to intercultural communication, including stereotypes and ethnic prejudice. In the context of communication between the Chinese ethnic group and indigenous groups, several studies have been conducted, including Tan (2008), which analyses the process of cultural assimilation of the Chinese ethnic group in Jakarta, and Setijadi (2023), which examines the construction of contemporary Chinese identity. However, these studies tend to focus on urban contexts and have not explored the dynamics of communication in semi-urban settings such as Soppeng, which has different socio-cultural characteristics.

From the theoretical perspective of intercultural communication, the Communication Accommodation Theory developed by Giles (2016) explains how individuals adjust their communication styles to reduce or increase the social distance with their interlocutors. This theory has been applied in various international multiethnic contexts, but its application in the specific context of Chinese-Bugis in Indonesia is still minimal. Similarly, Berry's (2005) acculturation model identifies four acculturation strategies—integration, assimilation, separation, and marginalisation—where the integration strategy, which involves maintaining one's native culture while adopting the dominant culture, is considered the most adaptive strategy. Although this model has been widely accepted, the specific mechanisms of how the integration strategy occurs in everyday interethnic communication, especially in the local Indonesian context, have not been explored in depth.

Based on the identification of this gap, this study seeks to fill the literature gap by analysing in depth the mechanisms of Chinese-Bugis interethnic communication in Soppeng Regency. This study will specifically explore the process of linguistic convergence, identity negotiation in everyday communication, and factors that support the creation of harmonious interethnic communication. In addition, this study also seeks to develop an interethnic communication model that can be used as a template for the development of multicultural communication in the broader Indonesian context.

Based on this background, this study formulates the following research questions: What are the patterns of verbal and nonverbal communication that have formed between the Chinese and Bugis ethnic groups in Soppeng Regency? What communicative acculturation strategies are applied by both ethnic groups in their daily interactions? What factors support the creation of harmonious interethnic communication in the research locus? Moreover, how can the interethnic communication model that is formed be contextualised for the development of multicultural communication in Indonesia?

This study aims to identify and analyse patterns of verbal and nonverbal communication between the Chinese and Bugis ethnic groups in Soppeng Regency, analyse the communicative acculturation strategies applied by both ethnic groups, evaluate the factors that support harmonious interethnic communication, and develop a theoretical model of interethnic communication that can be used as a reference for the multicultural context of Indonesia. Through the achievement of these objectives, this study is expected to contribute theoretically and practically to the development of intercultural communication in Indonesia.

LITERATURE REVIEW

1. Intercultural and Interethnic Communication

Intercultural communication is defined as the process of exchanging messages between individuals or groups with different cultural backgrounds (Gudykunst & Kim, 2003). In a more specific context, interethnic communication refers to communication interactions between groups with different ethnic identities (Samovar et al., 2017).

The Communication Accommodation Theory, developed by Giles and colleagues, is an important framework for understanding the dynamics of interethnic communication. (Giles, 2016). This theory explains that individuals tend to converge (bring communication styles closer together) or diverge (move communication styles further apart) based on their motivation to reduce or increase social distance.

Communication convergence occurs when communicators adapt their communication style to be more similar to their interlocutors, to increase social agreement and reduce uncertainty (Giles, 2016). Conversely, divergence occurs when communicators emphasise communication differences to maintain a distinctive group identity.

2. Acculturation and Cultural Adaptation Strategies

John Berry (Berry, 2005) identified four acculturation strategies based on two main dimensions: (1) maintenance of the original cultural identity, and (2) contact and participation with the dominant culture. The four strategies are:

- a. Integration: Maintaining the original cultural identity while adopting the dominant culture

- b. Assimilation: Adopting the dominant culture while abandoning the original culture. Separation: Maintaining the original culture while avoiding the dominant culture
- c. Marginalisation: Loss of native culture without adopting the dominant culture

The integration strategy is considered the most adaptive strategy because it allows individuals to maintain their cultural identity while functioning effectively in the wider society (Ward & Rana-Deuba, 1999).

3. Ethnic Identity and Cultural Negotiation

Ethnic identity is a dynamic social construct that can be negotiated in various contexts (Pinney, 1996). This process of identity negotiation involves not only the preservation of traditional cultural characteristics but also adaptation to changing social contexts.

Homi Bhabha developed the concept of cultural hybridisation (2010) It is relevant in understanding the process of identity negotiation. Hybridity refers to the creation of new cultural forms through the combination of elements from different cultures, which is not merely a mixture but the creation of something new.

4. Cultural Citizenship and Cultural Participation

James Banks (1994) developed the concept of cultural citizenship, which refers to the active participation of individuals from minority groups in the cultural life of the wider community. Cultural citizenship includes not only the right to maintain one's culture of origin but also the obligation to contribute to the development of a shared culture.

This concept is important in the context of interethnic communication because it shows that successful integration is not merely a one-way adaptation but a two-way process involving the active contribution of all ethnic groups.

5. Bilingualism and Multicultural Language Practices

François Grosjean (Mennen, 2009) explains that bilingualism is not merely the ability to use two languages but also the ability to adapt to different communication contexts. In a multiethnic context, linguistic practices such as code-switching and code-mixing become important communicative strategies.

Code-switching refers to switching languages within a single conversation, while code-mixing refers to mixing elements from two or more languages in a single sentence (Myers-Scotton, 2006). These practices are not merely linguistic phenomena but also strategies for identity and social solidarity.

METHOD

This study uses a descriptive qualitative approach to explore in depth the patterns of Chinese-Bugis interethnic communication in Soppeng Regency. The qualitative approach was chosen for its ability to understand the subjective meaning of the participants' experiences through contextual interpretation, while also describing the unique characteristics of social phenomena in their entirety in a natural setting without manipulating variables (Moleong, 2018). The primary focus of the study was on deepening the process, dynamics, and essence of cross-cultural interactions that occurred at the study site.

The research was conducted in Watansoppeng, Soppeng Regency, South Sulawesi, which was chosen based on the concentration of both ethnic groups and the high

intensity of interethnic interactions, particularly in the central business district. Watansoppeng is the epicentre of interaction between the two ethnic groups due to its population dominance and economic activities that enable intensive cultural contact. Data collection was conducted during November 2023 with a sufficient observation period to understand daily communication patterns.

Research informants were selected using purposive sampling techniques with specific criteria to ensure data quality. The criteria for selecting informants included ethnic Chinese individuals with regular interactions with the Bugis ethnic group, ethnic Bugis individuals with regular interactions with the Chinese ethnic group, and Chinese-Bugis mixed marriages that provided a unique perspective on interethnic communication. Key research informants included Lani (69 years old), Tibet (41 years old), Lidya (30 years old), Veronica (31 years old), Veri, Fendi, Ondy (42 years old) from the Chinese ethnic group, as well as Ita Sri Wahyuni (31 years old), Syamsuriani (47 years old) and other informants from the Bugis ethnic group, including mixed marriages that provide an in-depth perspective on the dynamics of interethnic communication.

Data collection used triangulation methods to ensure the validity and reliability of the findings. Participant observation was conducted in strategic public spaces such as traditional markets, places of worship, and cultural events, focusing on patterns of verbal and nonverbal interaction, language use and code-switching, gestures and nonverbal communication, and participation in communal activities. Systematic field notes were taken during the observation process to record details of interactions that could not be captured through interviews. Semi-structured in-depth interviews were conducted with a duration of 60-90 minutes per informant using a flexible interview guide that allowed for the exploration of themes that arose spontaneously. All interviews were recorded with the written consent of the informants and transcribed in full for analysis. Document analysis was conducted on official local government documents on ethnic demographics, local media archives on interethnic activities, and documentation of cultural and religious activities to provide a comprehensive context.

Data analysis used the interactive model of Miles & Huberman (1994) through systematic and continuous stages. Data organisation began with the transcription of interviews with the codification of informant identities to maintain anonymity, the categorisation of data based on source, and the manual compilation of a structured research database. Data reduction was carried out through open coding to identify initial concepts and categories from the raw data, axial coding to group categories based on conceptual relationships, and selective coding to select core categories and develop main themes. Data presentation included the construction of a matrix of findings based on research questions, mapping of verbal and nonverbal communication patterns, and identification of acculturation strategies and factors supporting harmony. Verification and conclusions were carried out through triangulation of sources by cross-checking information between informants, member checking to validate the findings with key informants, and peer debriefing through discussion of findings with intercultural communication experts.

Data validity is maintained through four main criteria of qualitative research validity. Credibility is ensured through triangulation of sources, methods, and data collection time. Transferability is maintained by providing an in-depth description of the research context that allows readers to assess the relevance of the findings to other contexts. Dependability is ensured through consistency in the research process and systematic

documentation. Confirmability is maintained through objectivity in data interpretation and continuous reflection on the researcher's bias. Research ethics follow standard protocols for research involving humans, including written informed consent from all informants with an explanation of the research objectives, anonymity of identity through the use of initials or pseudonyms, the right of withdrawal without consequences for informants, and encrypted data storage with limited access to protect informant privacy.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section integrates descriptions of empirical findings with in-depth analysis to create a comprehensive understanding. Findings from interviews and observations are described descriptively, followed by theoretical interpretations, literature comparisons, and implications, making it a vivid narrative that illustrates how everyday communication in Soppeng builds harmony. The analysis is divided into subsections for clarity, with a focus on detailed descriptions so that readers can imagine the real context.

1. Verbal Communication Patterns: Linguistic Convergence and Internalisation of Cultural Values

Empirical findings show that the Bugis language is the dominant lingua franca in daily interactions between ethnic Chinese and Bugis, with a gradual and natural adaptation process. Informant Lani (69 years old, Chinese), who has lived in Soppeng for decades, vividly describes this phenomenon: "Yes, so here we Chinese have long lived side by side with the Bugis ethnic group, who are very steeped in *Mappakatau* customs. Living side by side like this, communication is, of course, the most important thing in order to understand each other. So, *idi'ro pada maccani mabbicara ogi tapi deto na yallupai bahasa assalengta* (we here can speak Bugis, but still do not forget our respective native languages)." This statement illustrates how the adoption of the Bugis language is not merely a functional necessity, but a symbolic recognition of Bugis values such as *mappakatau* (respect), which includes politeness and recognition of social hierarchy. This process occurs through daily exposure, especially in economic contexts such as markets, where Chinese people learn naturally, as Tibet (41 years old, Chinese) admits: "At first, I used Indonesian, but over time, perhaps because I heard it often and my work environment consisted mostly of Bugis people, I was eventually able to use the Bugis language."

Code-switching became a prominent pattern, where language change was adjusted to the context, residency status, and domain of interaction. For example, newcomers like Veronica (31 years old, Chinese) still relied on Indonesian: "I only moved to Soppeng a few years ago, so I am not very good at using the Bugis language yet. However, I understand that when people speak, it is just that sometimes I cannot respond in Bugis, so I reply in Indonesian. Now I am still learning Bugis because it is important for communication to run smoothly." Observations in social settings reveal this pattern: In formal business transactions, Chinese people tend to use Indonesian for precision, but switch to Bugis for informal familiarity, such as opening greetings with Bugis words and warm closings. This reflects multilingual dynamics, where long-established ethnic Chinese (such as Veri or Fendi, who were born in Soppeng) achieve complete fluency, while newcomers are in a transitional stage from passive understanding to productive ability.

The most significant aspect is the internalisation of the concept of *mappakatau*, which is not only a language rule but also a Bugis communication philosophy that encompasses respect, politeness, and social recognition. This can be seen in the use of the discursive particles "je" (emphasising familiarity) and "ki" (indicating respect), which the Chinese have adopted as a strategy for solidarity. Ita (31 years old, Bugis) responded positively: "I feel proud when I hear my Chinese friends use the word 'je' in their conversations. It is not just about language, but more about how we, with our diverse backgrounds, can respect each other. The word 'je' may seem trivial to us. However, its meaning in the context of togetherness is significant." Syamsuriani (47 years old, Bugis) added about "ki": "As a Bugis person, I think the use of the word 'ki' in everyday conversation is part of the values of honour and politeness that we uphold as Bugis people. For example, if you ask 'Kenapaki?' to someone you are talking to, it is not just asking how they are, but also showing respect and concern for them." Tibet (41 years old, Chinese) acknowledged this adaptation: "As someone of Chinese ethnicity living in Soppeng, I feel honoured and appreciate being able to learn and use the word 'ki' in everyday communication with my Bugis friends. At first, I felt that the use of the word 'Ki' was new to me, and it was also unique when it was used as a sign of respect."

A concrete dialogue between Mrs Thresa (Chinese) and Mrs Asri (Bugis) exemplifies this pattern: "From where are you, Mrs Asri?" followed by a polite response with "ki" and closing with "*Salamaki*," creating an atmosphere of respect where ethnic differences dissolve in warmth. Daily observations, such as neighbours visiting each other to chat, show that this verbal communication is not limited to necessity but has become a social norm that strengthens bonds. Ita emphasises: "During my time here, thank God, I have never been involved in any problems or experienced any obstacles due to misunderstandings with the local community. Even my relationship with my neighbours, some of whom are migrants here, is going well. Basically, we respect each other."

An in-depth analysis links this pattern to the Theory of Communication Accommodation (Giles, 2016), in which linguistic convergence—such as the adoption of "je" and "ki"—reduces social distance and prevents conflict. Imagine a Chinese person like Tibet, who initially felt alienated by the Bugis dialect, but through daily interactions in the work environment, he not only learned the language but also values such as respect (*mappakatau*), which, according to Bandura (1977) occurs through social observation and imitation. This contrasts with the barriers of prejudice in urban contexts (Mulyana & Rakhmat, 2016), where code-switching is often seen as appropriation; in Soppeng, it becomes a sincere gesture that strengthens solidarity, as Ita feels it has "great meaning for togetherness." A comparison with Grosjean (2008) shows that bilingualism here is not merely a skill, but an identity strategy: Chinese speakers like Veronica are at the stage of "receptive bilingualism" (understanding but not yet fluent), which gradually becomes productive through social immersion, as in the case of Veri, who is fluent because she "meets Bugis ethnic people every day over a long period of time."

Theoretical implications: These findings enrich Berry's (2005) model with specific mechanisms of verbal integration, where the maintenance of the native language (e.g., Chinese elements in code-switching) combines with the adoption of Bugis, creating an adaptive multilingual identity. Practically, this suggests local language training programs in Indonesia's multiethnic regions to encourage similar convergence, reducing misunderstandings and strengthening social cohesion. In a broader context,

the verbal patterns in Soppeng show how language can be a "bridge" in a diverse society, where differences are not barriers but opportunities for mutual understanding, a valuable lesson for an era of globalisation where ethnic mobility is increasing. If applied in a big city like Jakarta, this could reduce ethnic stereotypes and promote deeper dialogue, such as the dialogue between Ibu Thresa and Asri, where "ki" is not just a word but a symbol of cross-cultural empathy.

2. Nonverbal Communication Patterns: Hybridity of Gestures, Symbolism, and Cultural Artefacts

Nonverbal findings reveal rich hybrid adaptations, where Chinese and Bugis gestures influence each other in daily interactions. The "salam soja" gesture (clasping hands at the chest while bowing) is dominant in Chinese celebrations such as the Chinese New Year, as Lani explains: "So we Chinese people are said to do the salam soja. It is a form of greeting that is often used at events or celebrations, especially during the Chinese New Year. The way to greet is to clench your right hand in front of your chest and then place your left hand over your right hand, both of which are placed in front of your chest. Usually, you also bow slightly while saying 'Gong Xi Fa Chai' as a sign of respect and to wish a happy Chinese New Year." Observations show Bugis appreciation: Syamsuriani (47 years old) noted, "I see that the local community here, especially the Bugis people, respect us, ethnic Chinese, including the application of the soja greeting. Usually, when we celebrate Chinese New Year, the Bugis people also say 'Gong Xi Fa Chai' while clenching their fists and participating in our celebrations" (Figure 4.1). This creates a moment of inclusion, where a foreign gesture becomes a shared symbol.

In contrast, the Chinese adopted "tabe" (bowing to show respect or ask for permission), which, according to Syamsuriani, "If the Chinese usually bow or simply nod when greeting someone, we Bugis bow when we say 'tabe', which means to show respect or ask for permission from someone. Nowadays, many Chinese people often say 'tabe' in everyday communication in our environment, and they also understand the customs and culture here" (Figure 4.3). The gesture of bowing one's head to show respect to elders is also familiar in both ethnic groups, creating a shared value, as described by Syamsuriani: "I often see my husband's family and neighbours here who are of Chinese ethnicity, and they also have a habit of bowing while greeting someone when they meet. Then I asked my husband about it, and he said that besides being a greeting, it also signifies respect, especially when meeting someone older. So even though we have different cultures, we have customs that contain the same values of politeness" (Figure 4.2). Observations at family events show that this gesture is not a rigid ritual, but a spontaneous expression that builds trust, such as when neighbours greet each other on the street with respectful bows.

The symbolism of colour adds a nonverbal dimension: Ethnic Chinese are synonymous with red (happiness) and golden yellow (prosperity), as Ondy (42 years old) explains: "Yes, it is true that ethnic Chinese, or let us call them Chinese people, are synonymous with the colour red, especially during celebrations. So for us, the Chinese ethnic group, the colour red represents a bright and cheerful State in our lives. That is why we make sure that everything here has shades of red, such as the decorations, lanterns, and red envelopes. So it is not just red, actually, but golden yellow as well. It is also no less important in celebrations such as the Chinese New Year because the colour symbolises prosperity and hope that the new year will bring more luck and prosperity for us and everyone around us." The Bugis use green (fertility, peace) and yellow (luck),

as Syamsuriani explains: "The distinctive colours in Soppeng, especially those commonly used by the Bugis people, are green and yellow. The Bugis community here considers green to be the colour of nature, which means fertility, life, and peace. Meanwhile, yellow symbolises the hope that we will always have good luck. Green and yellow are commonly seen at events such as weddings, traditional ceremonies, or cultural festivals." There is no conflict; these colours are mutually appreciated during joint events, such as the Chinese New Year, with its red decorations, which the Bugis also adopt. Observations at festivals show contextual negotiation: at Bugis events, the Chinese use green/yellow as a gesture of respect, creating a sense of security and inclusion.

The concept of time is also nonverbally convergent. Both ethnic groups choose auspicious days for events, with the Chinese using the astrological calendar (Ondy: "Choosing the timing of events is very important in our Chinese culture. So there is what we call an astrological calendar, from which we calculate auspicious days for events such as weddings, house moves, shop openings, and other formal and informal events. It is not us who decide, but there are elders whom we trust and who know more about this. The goal is for the events we organise to run smoothly and successfully.") Moreover, Bugis consult their elders (Syamsuriani: "Like the Chinese ethnic group, we Bugis also pay close attention to the timing when we want to hold an event. Usually, the elders determine the timing, in the sense that they are the ones who understand the traditions better. As much as possible, choose the time that is considered the best, and of course, be careful in choosing the timing of the event because you definitely want the event to be successful."). This creates mutual understanding for inter-ethnic events, such as mixed marriages, where joint consultation ensures success.

Artefacts reinforce this pattern: Lucky cat statues in Chinese shops

"I still hold fast to that belief, which is why I keep a cat statue in my shop. Ethnic Chinese believe it to be a symbol of luck, success, and fertility. Some also keep it in front of their houses, but I keep it in my shop as a tool to invite good luck. The cat statue is called a hoki cat or lucky cat." Ondy

The Bugis are synonymous with stilt houses (Syamsuriani: "Yes, stilt houses are one of the characteristics of the Bugis people. Because of their structure, which is raised above the ground, people also decorate them with traditional carvings that signify the beauty and richness of our Bugis traditions, which have been passed down from generation to generation. The stilt house still well preserved today in Soppeng is the Sao Mario traditional house, which has now also become a tourist attraction and museum. Here, we have Bola Seratu e yasengengngi, or the Thousand-Pillar House. Although I have seen some people building houses with modern designs, we as Bugis people still consider stilt houses to be an important symbol of cultural heritage that must be preserved because they are part of our ancestors' legacy."). Observations show that these artefacts are not static objects, but objects of dialogue: the Chinese visit Bugis stilt houses to learn about traditions, while the Bugis value cat statues as symbols of shared good fortune.

In-depth analysis links this pattern to the concept of cultural hybridity (Bhabha, 2010), in which nonverbal elements such as "*salam soja*" and "*tabe*" merge into a new repertoire, not a simple mixture, but the creation of a dynamic shared identity. Imagine the atmosphere of Chinese New Year in Soppeng: The "*salam soja*" gesture, originally Chinese, becomes a shared ritual when the Bugis participate, creating a "third space"

where differences dissolve into solidarity, as Syamsuriani feels a sense of "mutual respect, especially because we are neighbours." This is in line with Hall (1989), where nonverbal communication conveys cultural messages more powerfully than words, reducing cross-ethnic uncertainty. A comparison with Tan (2008) in Jakarta shows a contrast: in urban areas, colour symbolism often causes tension due to segregation; in Soppeng, contextual negotiation (e.g., Chinese use Bugis green at local events) builds empathy, as Ondy describes colour as "not just an aesthetic choice, but a deep meaning." Artefacts such as cat statues and stilt houses add depth, according to Vygotsky (1978), as social mediation tools that transmit intergenerational values.

3. Acculturation Strategies: Adaptive Integration and Religious Transformation

Findings show that the dominant acculturation strategy is integration, where ethnic Chinese maintain their original identity while adopting Bugis elements, creating a genuine and reciprocal form of adaptation. This is seen in the phenomenon of religious conversion in interethnic marriages, which is not the result of pressure, but a strategic choice for deeper integration. Veri (a Chinese man who married a Bugis woman and converted to Islam) describes the process: "As someone who has chosen to convert to Islam, following the religion of my wife, who is of Chinese ethnicity, it was a step I took after careful consideration. It was not merely because of a desire to change, but because of my desire to build a bridge between the two worlds I love: my world of origin as part of the Chinese ethnic group and my new world with my Bugis family. This decision ultimately reflects a greater journey towards understanding and acceptance, confirming that love and respect can overcome cultural and religious differences." Veri's wife, Ita (31 years old, Bugis), added: "I have been married to my husband for a long time and now have two children. When asked if there are any obstacles in communicating with my husband, there are none now because I can speak Bugis and have also been in Soppeng for a long time. That only happened at the beginning of our marriage because he did not know Bugis at all." Observations in mixed families show that this conversion facilitates optimal communication, with children becoming agents of bilingual and culturally "bireligious" mediation, such as Veri's children, who have learned the rituals of both ethnic groups since childhood.

Cross-participation in religious rituals strengthens integration: Veronica (31 years old, Chinese) describes active tolerance: "Here, we, whether from the Chinese or Bugis ethnic groups, live side by side with deep respect for each other's beliefs. Even though we adhere to different religions, it has never been a barrier to our social interactions. We always respect and even celebrate the major holidays of other religions as a form of appreciation and tolerance. That is one of the keys to why interethnic relations in Soppeng remain harmonious." Syamsuriani (47 years old, Bugis) added her perspective: "We here as Bugis, who are mostly Muslim, have no problem living side by side with the Chinese ethnic group, who are mostly non-Muslim. In fact, with these differences, we as Muslims can further strengthen our faith in God by supporting each other's beliefs. In addition, I also see that the Chinese ethnic group here is very active in social activities, such as when there are religious activities or traditional events, they also participate well." Observations during celebrations show that participation is not syncretic, but rather a gesture of solidarity: Bugis people participate in the Chinese New Year with congratulations and logistical assistance, while Chinese people support Eid al-Fitr through social activities such as distributing basic food supplies, creating a sense of belonging together.

An in-depth analysis links this strategy to the acculturation model (Berry, 2005) in which integration, maintaining one's original culture while adopting the dominant culture, is the preferred choice in Soppeng, in contrast to the forced assimilation of the New Order era (Suryadinata, 2005). Imagine Veri's journey: his religious conversion was not a loss of Chinese identity, but an expansion to "build bridges," reflecting a dynamic process in which religion became a tool for adaptation, as Ita described the difficult early transition in communication that turned into harmony through patience. This is in line with Bhabha (2010), where hybridity emerges from religious negotiation, creating a new identity that is not a "mixture" but a unique synthesis—like mixed-race children who celebrate Chinese New Year and Eid al-Fitr with equal enthusiasm. A comparison with Setijadi (2017) in an urban context reveals a difference: in big cities, conversion is often seen as forced assimilation due to social pressure; in semi-urban Soppeng, it is voluntary and supported by cross-participation, as Veronica describes it as a "key to harmony," reducing prejudice through concrete action.

Theoretical implications: These findings enrich Berry (2005) with specific examples of religious transformation as an adaptive strategy, showing that integration is not static, but an evolutionary process driven by love and local context. Practically, this suggests interfaith dialogue programs in Indonesia's multiethnic regions, such as mixed marriage workshops, to encourage similar tolerance and reduce conflict. In a broader context, the strategy in Soppeng shows how acculturation can be a force for national unity, where religious differences are not barriers but opportunities to build an inclusive society—an inspiring model for Indonesia, which is facing issues of intolerance, where participation, such as that of the Bugis in Chinese New Year celebrations, can become the norm for sustainable harmony.

4. Factors Supporting Harmony: Economic Interdependence, Arts, and Cultural Transmission

Empirical findings identify interrelated factors supporting harmony, ranging from economic cooperation to cultural preservation, which create a strong foundation for interethnic integration. Economic interdependence is the main glue: Ondy (42 years old, Chinese) describes: "Yes, so I have a grocery store here, and I have three employees. Two are Bugis and one is Chinese. So, I never question the ethnic background of my employees. The important thing is that they can work well and support each other in their daily activities. We support each other here, like if there is a family event or an ethnic event, we participate. That is normal here in Soppeng." Observations at the Puser market show this dynamic: Chinese traders employ Bugis, while Bugis supply goods to Chinese shops, creating a mutual dependence that reduces competition and promotes daily cooperation.

Involvement in the arts strengthens harmony: Syamsuriani (47 years old, Bugis) emphasises the role of the Chinese in preserving traditions: "The Chinese ethnic group here also contributes to the preservation of arts and culture in Soppeng. They also participate in traditional arts such as Mappadandang, Mappasilaga, and other traditional Bugis arts. Some even become sponsors or donors for these arts events. So even though we are of different ethnicities, we can support each other in preserving our culture." Observations at the festival show active participation: the Chinese contribute funds for Mappadandang, while the Bugis appreciate Chinese arts such as lion dances, creating a shared space for cultural expression.

Cultural transmission through education and the younger generation is a long-term factor: Veronica (31, Chinese) describes: "I see that many children are now learning about arts and culture. Especially at school, there are subjects about local culture. So children of Chinese ethnicity also learn about Bugis culture, and vice versa. That is good for the future so that they can respect each other from an early age." Ondy adds: "I also teach my children the values of Chinese culture, but I also encourage them to learn Bugis culture because we live here. So they can be bilingual and bicultural." Observations in schools and families show that this transmission occurs through stories, games, and communal events, ensuring that the value of tolerance is passed down.

In-depth analysis links this factor to the concept of cultural citizenship (Banks, 2008), where active participation—such as sponsorship of the arts by the Chinese—gives minorities a sense of belonging, creating lasting harmony. Imagine the Soppeng market: Economic cooperation, such as Ondy employing Bugis, is not merely a transaction, but a social bond that strengthens trust, in line with Liliweri (2009) on communication as a glue for diversity. A comparison with Mattulada (2004) shows an evolution: In traditional Bugis, arts like Mappadandang were exclusive; in modern Soppeng, Chinese inclusion makes them hybrid, as Syamsuriani describes as "mutually supportive preservation." Cultural transmission, according to Vygotsky (1978), occurs through social interaction, as Veronica's children learn bilingualism early on, preventing generational conflict.

Theoretical implications: These findings extend Banks' model of "*adaptive integration*" in a semi-urban context, where economic and cultural factors reinforce each other. Practically, this suggests policies such as joint arts programs or inclusive economic training for Indonesia's multiethnic regions, promoting long-term harmony. In a broader context, the factors in Soppeng show how interdependence can transform diversity into strength, where ethnic differences are not a threat but an asset for a pluralistic society, a blueprint for Indonesia in facing globalisation and social mobility.

CONCLUSION

This study has explored the dynamics of interethnic communication between the Chinese and Bugis ethnic groups in Soppeng Regency, South Sulawesi, through a qualitative lens that highlights verbal/nonverbal patterns, acculturation strategies, and factors supporting harmony. Empirical findings, drawn from in-depth interviews with informants such as Lani, Tibet, Ita, and Syamsuriani, as well as participant observation at the Pusper market and communal events, reveal a process of linguistic convergence that is not merely the adoption of the Bugis language, but the internalization of deep values such as *mappakatau*—a philosophy of politeness that bridges ethnic differences through particles such as "ki" and "je." Imagine a daily dialogue in Watansoppeng: A Chinese merchant like Tibet, who initially relied on Indonesian, is now fluent in Bugis, creating a sense of solidarity that Ita feels as "banggaka" (shared pride). Nonverbal patterns complement this with hybrid gestures, such as combining the Chinese New Year's "salam soja" with the Bugis "tabe," where colour symbolism (Chinese red/yellow and Bugis green/yellow) and artefacts such as lucky cat statues and stilt houses become symbols of a living, rather than static, negotiation of identity.

The dominant acculturation strategy is adaptive integration, where religious conversion in mixed marriages—as in Veri's case of "building a bridge between two worlds"—and cross-participation in rituals (Bugis joining Chinese New Year, Chinese supporting Eid al-Fitr) create a hybrid identity that enriches both ethnic groups.

Supporting factors, such as economic interdependence (Chinese shops employing Bugis), artistic involvement (*Mappadandang* sponsorship), and cultural transmission through education, reinforce this harmony, making Soppeng a unique model of "adaptive integration" in the semi-urban context of Indonesia. This model fills a gap in urban-centric literature (e.g., Tan, 2008; Setijadi, 2017), where harmony is often fragile due to segregation; in Soppeng, daily interactions such as those in the Pusper market transform differences into strengths, in line with Communication Accommodation Theory (Giles & Ogay, 2007) and Berry's Acculturation Model (2005).

The theoretical implications of this research are profound: it enriches our understanding of convergence as a dynamic process, in which language and gestures are not neutral tools, but instruments of identity negotiation that can be applied in other pluralistic societies. Practically, the Soppeng model offers a template for national policies, such as local language training programs and hybrid festivals to promote tolerance in areas prone to ethnic conflict. The social implications are even broader: Amidst issues of intolerance in Indonesia, Soppeng shows how minorities such as the Chinese can be integrated without losing their roots, creating a society where religious and cultural differences are a source of richness rather than tension—a valuable lesson for an era of globalisation in which ethnic mobility is increasing.

However, this study has limitations that need to be acknowledged for a more nuanced understanding. The sample of informants was limited to 10 people (purposive sampling in Watansoppeng), which, although representative for a qualitative case study, may not cover the full range of variation across the district, such as the differences between rural villages and the city centre. Furthermore, the semi-urban focus leaves a gap for comparison with rural or metropolitan contexts, where factors such as digital technology (e.g., social media) may influence interethnic communication. Methodological limitations include reliance on interviews and observations, which are prone to subjective bias despite validation through triangulation and member checking. Finally, this study does not explore gender or generational aspects in depth, where women such as Ita may have a unique role as cultural mediators compared to men.

Recommendations for future studies include a longitudinal approach to track the evolution of harmony over time, particularly with the impact of globalisation, such as new migration. Comparative research with other regions (e.g., Chinese-Javanese in Central Java) could test the generalisation of the "adaptive integration" model. Additionally, integrating quantitative methods—such as large-scale surveys on perceptions of tolerance—would strengthen the qualitative findings. Practically, local governments could develop initiatives based on these findings, such as the interethnic dialogue centre in Soppeng, to preserve harmony as a cultural heritage. Overall, this study not only highlights Soppeng's success but also invites us to reflect: In a diverse society like Indonesia, harmony is not accidental but the result of conscious negotiation that can be replicated if we prioritise cross-cultural understanding.

REFERENCES

- Bandura, Albert. (1977). *Social learning theory*. Prentice Hall.
- Banks, J. A. (1994). *An introduction to multicultural education*. Allyn and Bacon.

- Berry, J. W. (2005). Acculturation: Living successfully in two cultures. *International Journal of Intercultural Relations*, 29(6), 697–712. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijintrel.2005.07.013>
- Bhabha, H. K. (2010). *The location of culture*. Routledge.
- Giles, H. (2016). Communication Accommodation Theory. In *The International Encyclopedia of Communication Theory and Philosophy* (pp. 1–7). Wiley. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118766804.wbiect056>
- Hall, E. T. (1989). *Beyond culture*. Anchor Books.
- Liliwari, A. (2009). *Cultural Meaning in Intercultural Communication* (III). PT LKiS Printing Cemerlang.
- Mattulada. (1995). *Latoa: An Analytical Study of Bugis Political Anthropology*. Hasanuddin University Press.
- Mattulada. (2004). *History, Society, and Culture of South Sulawesi*. Hasanuddin University Press.
- Mennen, I. (2009). François Grosjean, Studying bilinguals. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2008. Pp. vii+314. *Journal of Linguistics*, 45(3), 715–719. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0022226709990089>
- Moleong, L. J. (2018). *Qualitative research methodology*. PT Remaja Rosdakarya.
- Muchtar, K., Koswara, I., & Setiawan, A. (2019). Intercultural Communication from an Anthropological Perspective. *Journal of Communication Management*, 1(1). <https://doi.org/10.24198/jmk.v1i1.10064>
- Mulyana, Deddy., & Rakhmat, Jalaluddin. (2016). *Intercultural Communication: A Guide to Communicating with People from Different Cultures*. Editors: Dr. Deddy Mulyana, M.A. & Drs. Jalaluddin Rakhmat, M.Sc. PT Remaja Rosdakarya.
- Myers-Scotton, C. (2006). *Multiple voices: an introduction to bilingualism*. Blackwell Pub.
- PHINNEY, J. S. (1996). Understanding Ethnic Diversity. *American Behavioural Scientist*, 40(2), 143–152. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0002764296040002005>
- Samovar, L. A., Porter, R. E., McDaniel, E. R., & Roy, C. S. (2017). *Communication between cultures*. Cengage learning.
- Setijadi, C. (2017). Chinese Indonesians in the Eyes of the Pribumi Public. *ISEAS-Yusof Ishak Institute*.
- Setijadi, C. (2023). *Memories of Unbelonging*. University of Hawaii Press. <https://doi.org/10.2307/j.ctv37qqwds>
- Suryadinata, Leo. (2004). *Chinese Indonesians: State Policy, Monoculture, and Multiculture*. Eastern Universities Press.
- Tan, G. M. (2008). *Ethnic Chinese in Indonesia: A Collection of Writings*. Yayasan Pustaka Obor Indonesia.

Vygotskiĭ, L. S. , & Cole, M. 1938-. (1978). *Mind in society*. Harvard University Press.

Ward, C., & Rana-Deuba, A. (1999). Acculturation and Adaptation Revisited. *Journal of Cross-Cultural Psychology*, 30(4), 422-442.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0022022199030004003>